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(LITERATURE REVIEW)****For citation:** Shavazi Nargiz Nuralievna, Khusanova Durдона Togoyurodovna Optimization of early diagnosis and prevention of intrahepatic cholestasis in pregnant women (literature review), Journal of Reproductive Health and Uro-Nephrology Research 2025, vol.6, issue 1, pp. 43-49<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15110842>**Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyevna**3-son Akusherlik va ginekologiya kafedrasini mudiri, t.f.d., dotsent
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БЕРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)**

A rare class of severe inflammatory skin illnesses that are itchy and specifically linked to pregnancy and/or the first few days after giving birth is called intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy. Pregnant women have a high prevalence of cutaneous AD and an annual increase in incidence, similar to the overall population. The most recent data indicates that between 5 and 20% of pregnant women have dermatosis; in industrial cities and megalopolises, this percentage is significantly greater. Since only a few pregnant dermatoses have conclusive diagnostic tests, clinical diagnosis based on morphological criteria is still crucial. All of these conditions, however, share a common symptom: intense skin itching, which considerably lowers the pregnant woman's quality of life. One of the most urgent problems in modern medicine is the problem of allergic dermatoses, which is closely linked

to polyvalent sensitization of the population, the extensive use of polymeric materials in production and daily life, the unfavorable environmental conditions on the planet, and high solar activity that promotes their growth [Williams N.S., Strachan D.P., May R.J., Werfel T., Kapp A., 2015, Roy Patterson, Leslie K., 2013, Eisen M.A., Kaur S.L., Silm H.A., 2016].

These diseases have distinct processes of occurrence and characteristics that have not been well investigated. The primary factor, as stated by Vaughan Jones SA (2016), Engineer L., et al. (2015), Moin A. et al. (2018); Jomez ML, 2015; Black MM, et al. (2017), is a shift in the hormonal balance in a pregnant woman's body, which impacts the gastrointestinal tract, kidneys, cardiovascular activity, water-salt metabolism, immune and nervous system function, and more.

Intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy (ICP) is a serious social issue in addition to a medical one.

Multicenter scientific studies are still being conducted throughout the world to uncover more features of this issue, particularly novel pathogenetic causes and extra diagnostic standards for the emergence of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy. The process by which intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy develops has not yet been thoroughly investigated, despite a great deal of research. However, understanding the pathophysiology of this disease is a prerequisite for creating predictive and preventative strategies that are effective while taking social and ethical norms into consideration.

Large-scale efforts are being made in our nation to avoid somatic diseases in the populace and to diagnose them early. Additionally, there are several unresolved issues in the healthcare system, the most significant of which are the prevention of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy and early diagnosis. The following are complete steps to drastically enhance the healthcare system: "... expanding opportunities for high-quality medical care for mother and child, providing specialized and high-tech medical care and reducing infant and child mortality."

Based on this, the development of methods for early diagnosis and prevention of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy is currently of great importance. In this regard, conducting research aimed at improving the quality of life and reducing perinatal outcomes has served as a reason for searching for additional, new methods for early prognosis and prevention of this pathology in order to reduce perinatal mortality and childhood disability. Objective of the study: To identify prognostic predictors of the development of intrahepatic cholestasis in pregnant women and to develop early prevention measures. There has long been a belief that some pregnancy toxicoses with primary liver injury, which show up as jaundice, are present. Many researchers recognized the existence of liver damage with the onset of jaundice during the peak of severe toxicosis (eclampsia, uncontrollable vomiting) [6,35]. Brauer K. described the alleged toxicosis of pregnancy with primary liver injury for the first time, referring to it as toxic jaundice of pregnancy. Van den Velden provided a detailed description of this toxicosis's clinical manifestation. He indicates that, in addition to jaundice, the pregnant woman is bothered by itching, there may be vomiting, there is no enlargement of the liver and spleen, there are pronounced neuroasthenic phenomena (irritability, insomnia), the feces are acholic, pigments and protein are found in the urine. After childbirth, all these phenomena disappear, but jaundice can recur in subsequent pregnancies.

A similar description of toxic jaundice of pregnancy was also given by Mayer A. [16]. The clinical manifestations and symptoms of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy were first described by the physician F. Alfeld [24]. Subsequently, other researchers published about pregnancy-related toxicosis, which showed up as liver-derived jaundice and was referred to as embryogenic jaundice, paracholia, idiopathic pregnancy jaundice, hepatopathy of pregnancy, and toxic liver degeneration. N.A. Farber initially suggested the term "late toxicosis of pregnancy with liver syndrome" based on numerous observations, and later, as a more effective term, "cholestatic hepatitis of pregnancy" [9]. According to Courpas AS, Dudley AN, in 10% of cases cholestatic hepatitis can develop without preceding itching of the skin, often accompanied by pain in the epigastrium, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, in 5% of cases the liver enlarges. There may be complications in the form of cystopyelitis, gastritis, colitis. However, itching can occasionally happen without jaundice, and digestive issues and stomach pain are not usually noticeable. Many pregnant women report skin itching during relapses of this toxicosis, and the illness may worsen to a severe or "critical" state [24]. Several researchers have placed a high value on disruptions in the metabolism of female sex hormones, particularly estrogens, in the pathophysiology of CGD [28]. The idea that cholangioendocrine insufficiency is the cause of pregnant women's cholestatic hepatitis was put out by Farber N.A.

The consequences of CGD for the mother and child were different. The prognosis for the mother was considered favorable, for the children - poor. Children born to mothers who had CGD had severe hearing and speech impairments (Graf). According to Fredlander P., Osier M., perinatal mortality in this pathology reached 18%. The cause of death

in children was mainly pulmonary disorders with atelectasis and the development of hyaline membranes. In the treatment of cholestatic hepatitis of pregnant women, great difficulties arose in combating excruciating itching of the skin, due to which it was sometimes necessary to terminate the pregnancy. A number of researchers denied the possibility of the appearance of specific jaundice in pregnant women [24].

In addition to previous terms like "benign jaundice of pregnancy," "idiopathic jaundice of pregnancy," "bile thickening syndrome," and "cholestatic hepatitis of pregnancy," the term intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy (ICP) is now frequently used. According to its etiology, this condition is exclusively linked to pregnancy and is the second most common cause of jaundice in the third trimester of pregnancy, after viral hepatitis [8, 10, 26, 46]. It should be noted that 75% of pregnant women experience problems during pregnancy and childbirth, and the prevalence of chronic liver and biliary tract illnesses has climbed to 9.2% [50, 22]. Intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy is distributed differently in different countries of the world: in Chile - 15.1%, Sweden - 2%, Bolivia and China there is 1 case per 750 - 7000 pregnancies [19, 10, 15]. Cholestasis of pregnancy is extremely rare in Asian women [125]. In Switzerland, the incidence rate is 0.35%, in the United States of America - 0.01% [33].

Statistical data on the prevalence of intrahepatic cholestasis in Uzbekistan are currently unknown. Low prevalence rates of intrahepatic cholestasis in Europe indicate that this problem is underestimated, since mild forms of the disease, manifested by minor itching and mild increase in liver enzymes, are sometimes not diagnosed in time. Currently, early and accurate diagnosis of this disease leads to an increase in morbidity rates and allows for early prevention [10, 44]. Intrahepatic cholestasis is a pathological process, the pathogenesis of which is based on a decrease in bile flow in the absence of mechanical obstruction of the biliary tract. Morphologically, it is characterized by the accumulation of bile in liver cells and bile ducts, functionally - by a decrease in the canalicular flow of bile, clinically - by a delay in the blood of substances normally excreted with bile [22, 43, 36]. Intrahepatic cholestasis syndrome develops under the influence of drugs, infectious agents, and also as a result of autoimmune, metabolic or genetic factors [18, 28].

Depending on the extent of liver damage, intrahepatic cholestasis can be categorized as intralobular (hepatic tubular), which is caused by insufficient bile secretion by liver cells and bile ducts as a result of damage to cellular organelles, or interlobular (ductal), which is linked to the destruction and reduction of small interlobular ducts, ductules, and ducts [24,37,26]. Water, electrolytes, inorganic (such as heavy metal salts), and organic (bile acids and their salts, conjugated bilirubin, cholesterol, phospholipids, proteins, and cytokines) components make up the complex mixture that is bile. Bile acids (BA) are only produced by the liver. Cholesterol is converted into the two primary acids, cholic and chenodeoxycholic. Primary BA are converted into secondary bile acids—deoxycholic and a trace amount of lithocholic—by intestinal bacteria. The liver isomerizes secondary bile acids to produce tertiary bile acids, primarily ursodeoxycholic acid. The pathophysiology of cholestasis is thought to be significantly influenced by abnormalities in intrahepatic bile acid metabolism, which also contribute to the development of itching [29, 31, 44, 12]. Cholestasis can also arise as a result of changes in sodium-potassium ATPase activity and the fluidity of the basolateral membrane, which is a component of the hepatocyte structure.

Wilkinson ML, in an experiment conducted on rats, showed that ethinyl estradiol reduces the fluidity of sinusoidal plasma membranes. For instance, under the influence of androgens, damage to the microfilaments that control the tone and contraction of the canalliculi, or tight junctions, can compromise the integrity of the canalicular membrane. The demarcation barrier between hepatocytes is destroyed when estrogens cause tight junctions to rupture, allowing big molecules from the bloodstream to enter the canalliculi directly and regurgitating dissolved bile contents into the blood [49]. Electron microscopy reveals nonspecific alterations in the bile canalliculi, such as dilatation, edema, thickening and tortuosity, and loss of microvilli, irrespective of the cause of cholestasis. The Golgi apparatus vacuolates, the endoplasmic

reticulum enlarges, and copper-containing lysosomes proliferate when combined with protein. Vesicles around the tubules containing bile give hepatocytes «pinnate» appearance under light microscopy [28, 33].

Tiechmarm W. performed a liver biopsy in 20 pregnant women and showed that in benign cholestasis of pregnancy, the structure of the lobules and portal fields is preserved, there are no signs of inflammation and necrosis. Focal cholestasis with bile clots in dilated capillaries and bile pigment accumulation in nearby liver cells is the sole pathogenic symptom [34]. Other researchers verified these findings by observing dilated bile ducts with bile clots inside, which are mild indicators of localized cholestasis. The compaction of the hepatocyte's biliary pole and a decrease in the fluidity (absence of pores) of the canalicular membrane of hepatocytes with preserved intracellular transport are the pathogenic factors that cause an increase in the concentration of bile components in the hepatocyte in intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy, according to Wilkinson ML [28].

When conducting statistical studies, many foreign authors came to the conclusion that the risk of developing intrahepatic cholestasis is higher in primiparous women, as well as in the presence of multiple pregnancies. In subsequent pregnancies, in 40-60% of cases, a tendency to relapse of this disease is noted, while the disease manifests itself earlier and proceeds with more severe clinical symptoms [39, 42]. Many authors believe that the hereditary factor plays an important role in the occurrence of this disease. Thus, Eleoranta (2001) discovered a high frequency of HLA-DPB 1*0402 alleles among Chilean patients from one family, where the disease occurred in grandmothers, mothers and sisters, with repeatedly recurring cholestasis of pregnancy [111]. However, other authors believe that a family history of ICP is usually associated with the HLA-B8 and HLA-Bw6 haplotypes [11, 14, 29]. Loginov A.S. et al. showed that HLA-B8, which is often detected in active chronic liver disease, is an antigen associated with diseases of various etiologies but with common pathogenetic features. The authors regarded the HLA-B8 antigen as a "marker of hyperimmunity" in these patients. There are suggestions that the inheritance of this disease is linked to the X chromosome [44, 28].

In the last few years, foreign authors have published works that contain data on other genetic markers of cholestasis, including intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy: BSEP (bile salt export pump gene) is a gene responsible for the transport of bile salts, FIC1 (familial intrahepatic cholestasis 1 gene) is a gene of familial intrahepatic cholestasis, MDR3 (multiple drug resistance 3 gene) is a gene of multiple drug resistance encoding the formation of the MDR3 protein, which promotes the secretion of phospholipids into bile [12, 36, 37, 48]. The same data were obtained by other authors, who established a mutation in the MDR3 gene. It should be added that women who had cholestasis during pregnancy were heterozygous for this trait [11, 17, 35]. However, the pathogenesis of ICP is determined not only by genetic factors. The clinical and experimental data conducted allowed us to assume that low levels of selenium intake and the resulting decrease in glutathione peroxidase activity may be the cause of cholestasis development during pregnancy [17]. Seasonal fluctuations in the incidence of cholestasis in countries with a high prevalence of cholestasis during pregnancy indicate the influence of environmental factors [20, 15]. For example, in Finland and Sweden, ICP occurs more often in winter than in summer [33]. Some researchers believe that the incidence of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy increases in the spring and autumn periods [38, 46]. Many authors argue that the development of intrahepatic cholestasis is directly related to pregnancy. Pregnancy leads to the development of cholestasis syndrome due to thickening and increased viscosity of bile, decreased tone of the bile ducts and increased permeability of the bile capillaries, excessive accumulation of progesterone in the body, and disruption of estrogen and testosterone metabolism [22, 45, 35, 13].

Therefore, erythema of the palms and spider veins on the skin of the chest and back can be found upon inspection in 50% of women in the second half of physically preceding pregnancy. A biochemical analysis of blood serum during the final trimester of pregnancy reveals mild cholestasis, which is characterized by a moderate 1.5–2 times rise in alkaline phosphatase (AP) activity, as well as a moderate increase in cholesterol, α_1 - and α_2 -globulin levels, when compared to normal

values. γ -glutamyl transpeptidase (GGT) activity stays within typical bounds. Bile acid levels slightly rise as a result. Albumin, urea, and uric acid levels in the blood serum fall, whereas bilirubin levels and liver transaminase activity stay within normal ranges [23, 19, 27]. These alterations are risk factors for intrahepatic cholestasis formation and take place during the second and third trimesters of physiologically preceding pregnancy [25, 21, 12]. The majority of publications express an opinion regarding the contribution of pregnancy-related hormonal changes to the development of intrahepatic cholestasis. Pregnancy-related intrahepatic cholestasis is caused by the rapid rise in sex hormone production during pregnancy, which significantly increases the excretory load on the liver when paired with previous congenital constitutional inferiority of the liver enzyme systems [15, 16].

The pathophysiology of ICP is thought to be significantly impacted by an increase in the blood serum concentration of estrogens, which exacerbates bile acid secretion and results in cholestatic syndrome [44, 48, 22].

Leslie KK. gathered several pieces of evidence in their research that suggested estrogens were the main cause of the development of intrahepatic cholestasis during pregnancy. A significant amount of estrogens are produced by the fetoplacental complex, which are then converted and undergo metabolic alterations in the mother's liver. The low levels of these hormones in the urine of pregnant patients with ICP confirm that the hepatocytes in this patient group are unable to efficiently perform enzymatic inactivation and conjugation of steroid hormones with glucuronic and sulfuric acids, as most researchers have shown that there is no hyperproduction of estrogens in ICP [38, 50]. Oral contraceptives containing estrogen may cause nodular hyperplasia of the liver, portal vein and hepatic vein thrombosis, intrahepatic cholestasis, and regional liver necrosis [26].

Progesterone, which is used to reduce the risk of miscarriage, is also thought to be one of the external elements that contribute to ICP in women who are predisposed to it by their constitution [22, 44, 24]. Because more hormones are released during multiple pregnancies than during singleton pregnancies, it has been shown that the risk of getting ICP increases fivefold. However, women who have a singleton pregnancy and a hereditary tendency to intrahepatic cholestasis may be more susceptible to this condition [23, 34, 45]. There is also a connection between intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy and chronic or acute infection. When studying the blood serum of patients with ICP using the enzyme immunoassay method, high titers of IgG to the herpes simplex virus (HSV), high titers of IgG and IgM to cytomegalovirus (CMV), continuously recurring adenovirus infection confirmed by virological methods were detected for the first time [10, 43].

Thus, it is rational to assume that pregnancy-related intrahepatic cholestasis is a polyetiological condition caused by a combination of endogenous and extrinsic factors. During pregnancy, it shows up as a constitutional enzyme deficiency. Clinical and diagnostic criteria for intrahepatic cholestasis during pregnancy. A decrease in the quantity of bile secreted in the intestine, an excessive flow of bile elements into the blood, and the toxic effects of bile components on hepatocytes and biliary canals are the three main pathogenetic factors that lead to the development of clinical manifestations of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy. ICP usually appears in the third trimester of pregnancy.

Intense itching (without rash or other visible skin lesions) is the main and most common symptom of pregnancy-related cholestasis. Itching usually starts between weeks 28 and 30 of pregnancy in 87% of people. Jaundice may show up 1-4 weeks after itching starts in 20% of patients [26, 49, 5]. However, a number of scientists think that only 10.8% of ICP instances result in yellowing of the skin and mucous membranes [71, 18]. Unusual manifestations of this condition occur in 20% of cases, including early pregnancy ICP start, pregnancy itchiness without changes in liver enzymes, and postpartum worsening of the disease lasting up to 1-2 months [33, 15]. According to Teichmann W. et al., the earliest form of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy is skin itching throughout the first half of pregnancy [44]. Excoriations, sleeplessness, and increased weariness are caused by skin itching that is more noticeable on the trunk and outer surfaces of the limbs. Anorexia, steatorrhea (a typical symptom whose severity varies on the severity of cholestasis), nausea, and soreness in the epigastric area are also seen.

The primary cause of weight loss, reduced bone mineralization, and deficiencies in fat-soluble vitamins, particularly vitamin K, is malabsorption. In rare instances, vitamin K insufficiency results in uterine and cerebral hemorrhage as well as an increase in prothrombin time. This pathology's primary clinical manifestation is not necessarily jaundice.

After the appearance of jaundice, urine becomes dark in color, and feces become discolored. [49, 33, 42]. According to many authors, pain syndrome is not characteristic of intrahepatic cholestasis [18,46]. Germanov V.T. et al. point to a slight increase in the size of the liver and spleen, which can be detected using instrumental research methods, but Shekhtman M.M. et al. argued that hepatosplenomegaly is not characteristic of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnant women [22, 9]. Specific biochemical markers of intrahepatic cholestasis include alkaline phosphatase and gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, as well as leucine aminopeptidase and 5-nucleotidase [11,14]. ALP activity increases in cholestasis and to a minor extent in hepatocyte damage. An increase in GGT activity, which occurs in parallel with an increase in ALP activity, indicates a hepatobiliary origin of alkaline phosphatase. As a diagnostic sign, GGT activity has low specificity because it varies on numerous circumstances. These variables include alcohol use, some medicines, and disorders of the liver and biliary tract [36, 49]. The lack of an increase in GGT levels, however, is recognized as a diagnostic characteristic of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy and has been validated in numerous investigations [43, 50]. An rise in cholestasis indicators is more substantial than an increase in the activity of other transaminases. Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels typically rise two to three times in modern practice, while occasionally transaminase levels rise eight to ten times [45, 11, 47].

Another sensitive test for establishing the diagnosis of ICP is measuring the concentration of bile acids in the blood serum, the increase of which is recorded even before the appearance of visible clinical and biochemical signs of intrahepatic cholestasis [32, 14]. Determining the bile acid level in pregnant patients with cholestasis revealed that the fraction of primary bile acids varied noticeably in this group of patients. The ratio of cholic to chenodeoxycholic acid increases, the ratio of glycine to taurin decreases, and the amount of cholic acid rises while the level of chenodeoxycholic acid falls [38, 15]. The concentration of conjugated bile acids increased in the pool of bile acids and progesterone metabolites in the serum and urine of women with ICP, whereas the levels of unconjugated bile acids in intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy and in the physiological course of pregnancy remained unchanged. An increase in the concentration of sulfated metabolites of progesterone in the blood serum was also revealed in intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy [28, 11, 11, 48]. Bacq Y. et al. report that the pool of primary bile acids in pregnant cholestasis is 88% (cholic: 72.7%, chenodeoxycholic: 15.3%); secondary bile acids: 11.3%; and the level of tertiary (ursodeoxycholic) bile acids was found to be very low in comparison to the level of total bile acids [49, 50]. The maximum transport rate and the efficiency of transport on the trophoblast's fetal surface are both reduced in cholestasis, which also affects the placental transport of bile acids [40, 29, 48]. Osadchenko E. Yu. proposed a special scoring scale for assessing the severity of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy. A score of up to 10 indicates a mild degree of ICP, from 10 to 25 - of moderate severity, and more than 25 - of severe ICP. When establishing the severity of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy, it is necessary to take into account the assessments of the most characteristic subjective (skin itching) and objective clinical data, laboratory data (biochemical tests) and instrumental research methods, that is, those main criteria by which the presence of ICP is diagnosed [45].

Using the de Ritis coefficient (AST/ALA ratio), which is $1.33 + 0.42$ during the normal course of pregnancy and considerably declines (less than 0.7) with liver tissue damage, Pungina M. Yu (2003) evaluated the severity of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy. Compared to pregnant women without intrahepatic cholestasis, whose de Ritis coefficient was $1.46 + 0.61$, the average values for pregnant women with intrahepatic cholestasis fall between $1.09 + 0.32$.

This coefficient varies according to the severity of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy; in more severe cases, it falls to 0.23 to 0.38. Additionally, the author pointed out that an increase in transaminase levels on the day or two following birth is a characteristic of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy. This might be because the first day after delivery is when estrogens are released in large quantities. Furthermore, the de Ritis coefficient shows a slight decline [41]. There is a relative predominance of T-helpers with a marked shortage of T-suppressors in intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy, according to recent investigations on the immunological system of pregnant women with this condition. Other writers claim that the number of T-lymphocytes, as well as T-adrenaline and T-serotonin-sensitive lymphocytes, doubles during the second trimester of pregnancy. Theophylline-sensitive lymphocytes also proliferate throughout the third trimester. This explains the high rate of miscarriages and suggests a major pathogenetic role of immunological changes in ICP by immunosuppressing humoral reactions and boosting the cellular immune response [50, 47].

When intrahepatic cholestasis occurs during pregnancy, the activity of erythrocyte membrane-bound Na-K-ATPase, Ca-ATPase, and Mg-ATPase is markedly reduced. The intraerythrocytic levels of Ca and Na are higher than the Mg level in ICP. We were able to draw the conclusion that a high concentration of lithocholic acid impacts the morphofunctional state of erythrocytes based on these results as well as the found negative association between the serum concentration of lithocholic acid and the activity of ATPases (Na, K, Ca) [16].

In ICP, xenobiotic metabolism in the placenta is also impaired and its aromatase activity is reduced. In comparison with the control, significant inhibition of some cytochrome P450-dependent monooxygenases of the placenta was found. Active inhibition of cytochrome P450-dependent monooxygenases in the human placenta in ICP, *in vitro*, poses a potential risk to intrauterine fetal development [17]. In studies to determine the indices of blood flow velocity in the umbilical artery of the fetus in pregnant women with intrahepatic cholestasis, it was found that even a significant increase in bile acids in the mother's blood serum in ICP does not cause disruption of the uteroplacental and fetoplacental blood flow [33, 13]. The presence of intrahepatic cholestasis during pregnancy is associated with a high incidence of premature birth [27, 38, 17]. ICP also raises the risk of infections, issues with the urinary system, and heavy bleeding during childbirth [34, 12]. According to the authors, multiple pregnancies surpass 100%, and the prevalence of premature deliveries in this situation ranges from 10% to 60% [23, 26, 45]. The mother's prognosis is considered favorable if all illness symptoms disappear 8–15 days following delivery. Even though ICP recurs frequently throughout consecutive pregnancies, it is believed to leave no changes in the mother's liver. Only one instance of recurrent pregnant cholestasis leading to biliary cirrhosis and portal triad fibrosis, requiring orthotopic liver transplantation for severe causes, has been reported in recent literature [13, 46].

Despite having a favorable effect on the mother, ICP is linked to a high rate of perinatal mortality and can have a more severe effect on the fetus. Additionally, up to 35% of all deliveries were shown to have a higher risk of preterm birth, growth retardation, hypoxia, and fetal distress [8, 26, 47, 11]. The risk of fetal death with recurrent cholestasis is four times higher than in a normal pregnancy, according to Fisk NM et al., who cite a higher figure of 35% [7, 16]. Perinatal mortality with ICP is 4.7%, according to other publications. Meconium staining of amniotic fluid with ICP is seen in 25–50% of cases [18, 47]. According to Zecca E. et al. (2006), high bile acid levels during pregnancy-related intrahepatic cholestasis change how phospholipase A2 functions in the baby's alveoli, causing surfactant failure and raising the risk of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) in the newborn. The study found that the risk of having RDS was 2.5 times higher in the ICP group than in the control group, and that the incidence of RDS was twice as high in neonates whose mothers had ICP as in the control group [10,25]. Due to coagulopathy brought on by the mother's intestines' poor absorption of fat-soluble vitamins, such as vitamin K, ICP also raises the risk of fetal hemorrhage.

Based on all the data, it can be concluded that strict and regular monitoring of the intrauterine condition of the fetus is necessary.

Guidelines for the management and avoidance of intrahepatic cholestasis during pregnancy. Finding the "ideal" drug to improve biochemical blood parameters and reduce clinical symptoms is the aim of all treatments for intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy. In an effort to reduce bile acid production, small doses of phenobarbital have been used to treat ICP in the past ten years, but this treatment has not been successful [10, 48, 33]. Pregnant women with intrahepatic cholestasis were then treated with dexamethasone; however, it was later discovered that the medication had no appreciable impact on the patients' health [21, 27]. Cholestyramine is a lipid-lowering medication that has recently been developed to treat this condition. This medication reduces itching by mixing bile acids. Nevertheless, cholestyramine use will not result in an improvement in the fetus's health or the liver's biochemical characteristics. Impaired absorption of vitamin K can lead to complications such as blood clotting issues and steatorrhea. Using this medication during pregnancy may also result in acute cerebral hemorrhages in the fetus [39, 49].

To reduce itching, antihistamines and mild tranquilizers are often recommended [46]. In recent years, ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) has been used to treat ICP. This naturally occurring hydrophilic bile acid helps the body get rid of endogenous hydrophobic bile acids and possesses anti-apoptotic, anti-cholestatic, and immunomodulatory qualities [49, 50]. Because it has no adverse effects on the growing fetus, research indicates that this medicine is safe to take throughout pregnancy. In a comparison of the safety and efficacy of UDCA and cholestyramine at a dose of 8–10 mg/kg of body weight per day in the treatment of ICP, pregnant women receiving UDCA showed a statistically significant decrease in the intensity of skin itching and a decrease in the level of aminotransferases in the blood serum compared to patients receiving cholestyramine [49]. When compared to low doses (8–10 mg/kg/day), high dosages of ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA; 15 mg/kg/day) dramatically reduced blood levels of bilirubin and all enzymes, with no negative effects on the pregnant woman's or the fetus's health [44]. Without altering the concentration of lithocholic acid, UDCA therapy was associated with a decrease in cholic acid and an increase in chenodeoxycholic acid [34, 50].

Furthermore, it has been suggested that UDCA therapy encourages the biliary tract to excrete progesterone sulfated metabolites [29]. UDCA preparations have been shown to improve the fetus's prognosis by reducing the amount of bile acids transported from the mother to the fetus by reestablishing the placenta's ability to carry out normal bile acid transport [50]. Another recommended drug that influences important pathways in the pathophysiology of cholestasis is C-adenyl methionine. These pathways include suppression of Na-K-ATPase and other membrane transporters, as well as decreased hepatocyte membrane permeability. This medication promotes cell defense against bile acids and free radicals by increasing the synthesis and content of thiols. Treatment with C-adenyl methionine stabilizes some biochemical parameters and alleviates the intensity of itching in ICP [49, 50].

Given all of the foregoing, we may conclude that the current treatment modalities do not present the possibility of fully remitting the illness and halting the mother's liver function from deteriorating. Pregnancy itself imposes additional stress on the liver and all other organs and systems, and the use of several drugs, especially hepatotropic ones, exacerbates the condition [10, 26, 28, 47]. This forces us to look for more modern therapeutic strategies that allow us to influence the body's nonspecific response and enable the affected systems to function normally again. Examples of extracorporeal hemocorrection (ECH) techniques that have been widely adopted into clinical practice in recent years include transfusion operations of targeted quantitative and qualitative change of cellular, protein, water-electrolyte, enzymatic, and gas composition of blood in the extraorganismal perfusion circuit of blood circulation [2, 50]. The prevention and treatment of some pathological conditions have significantly improved as a result of the widespread use of these techniques in therapeutic and surgical clinics [1, 5, 6, 9, 15, 17].

The primary goal of extracorporeal procedures is to prevent the body's primary defenses—the immunological, excretory, microsomal, and monooxygenase systems—from failing by perfusing blood or plasma via sorbents, membranes, or filters and then extracting a portion

of them. The use of plasmapheresis (PA) in obstetric treatment is required because many pathological disorders in pregnant women arise in the context of alterations in the system that regulates the aggregate state of blood, circulation of vasoactive chemicals, and toxic substrates.

Because PA affects these parameters, it has a therapeutic effect [4, 19, 23, 50]. The two main types of plasmapheresis at the moment are intermittent (discrete) PA and gravity continuous PA with the appropriate equipment. The majority of domestic physicians favor intermittent saccular PA because of its benefits, which include ease of use, accessibility, the ability to perform PA on multiple patients at once, the elimination of the need for main vein catheterization, and the need for specialized equipment preparation for work [2, 12, 16, 33].

Toxic substances, autoantibodies, immune complexes (antigen-antibody), metabolic products, and parts of damaged tissues and cells are removed from the bloodstream; cellular cleaning systems and formed blood elements are deplasmized; hematopoietic, stromal, and immunocompetent cells are more functional and their vital activity changes; the phagocytic system and natural organs «purification» are unblocked; the phenomenon of optical turbidity of plasma is eliminated; microcirculation is improved, and reinfused blood elements are affected extracorporeally [2, 13, 16, 19, 21, 50]. Other writers claim that the positive effects of PA are linked to the restoration of the liver and kidneys' natural detoxification mechanisms in addition to the mechanical removal of some toxins and the enhancement of blood homeostasis [3, 40].

Plasmapheresis also has an antioxidant effect. Eliminating the body's free radical oxidation products increases the activity of antioxidant defense factors. The next effect of plasmapheresis is immunocorrection. This effect ensures the removal of blood-borne complement system components, immunoglobulins, and antigen-antibody complexes. Additionally, PA must improve the performance of cell membranes, which are in charge of absorbing poisonous substances during prolonged intoxication. The microcirculation system and the condition of vascular tone may be connected to the reocorrective action as PA and other efferent strategies of impact change the ratio of vasoactive substances in the blood plasma.

These mechanisms work together to promote microcirculation, activate transcapillary exchange, optimize the oxygen regime, decrease blood viscosity, boost erythrocyte deformability, and restore normal tissue metabolism. The main factors that determine functional and homeostatic reactions associated with the use of efferent therapy methods (additional effects) are the influence of a blood stabilizer, typically heparin, the introduction of infusion, transfusion, and drugs of targeted action, as well as the use of replacement therapy, whose options are greatly increased against the backdrop of efferent therapy. It is feasible to both level out or lessen the adverse effects of the treatment and greatly enhance the specific effects of PA thanks to unique transfusion and medication programs. The efficacy of treatment for patients with elevated levels of cholesterol and bilirubin, which cause atherosclerotic vascular lesions, xanthomatosis, jaundice, and itching by penetrating tissues and organs, is explained by the diffusion mechanism of PA action. These metabolites diffuse from tissues and organs more easily when plasma is removed from the bloodstream because it lowers their concentration in the serum. This leads to xanthoma regression, jaundice, itching, and atherosclerotic vascular lesions [17, 18, 42]. Because of the effects that have been demonstrated, plasmapheresis is therefore commonly used to prevent and treat multiple organ failure syndrome, HELLP syndrome, placental insufficiency of various causes, early and late toxicosis, and various extragenital pathologies [1, 3, 7, 9, 11, 12, 16, 25, 34, 47, 50]. According to a study of the literature, pregnant patients with intrahepatic cholestasis can have a variety of plasmapheresis treatments, with different replacement solution quality and plasma removal volumes.

Accordingly, Deryabina N.V. et al. (2003) observed a strong treatment effect because of the detoxifying, immunocorrective, and strong antioxidant effects of PA when they performed plasmapheresis on pregnant women with intrahepatic cholestasis using plasma filters «Dew» on the device «Phoenix», removing 600–800 ml of plasma per session. However, the qualitative makeup and quantities of plasma substitution were not considered by the studies [29, 30]. In order

to remove 1.3 liters of circulating plasma and replace it with a 5% albumin solution, Warren JE et al. (2004) employed centrifugal plasmapheresis in a pregnant lady who had recurrent cholestasis in each successive pregnancy due to the ineffectiveness of traditional therapy. For 32 weeks, PA procedures were performed every three to five days while platelet counts, calcium levels, and blood clotting times were tracked. The authors also noted a notable clinical benefit and the possibility of prolonging pregnancy to 36–37 weeks of gestation [19]. Most writers believe that this is the most effective and trouble-free method of removing moderate (30%) or medium (31–60%) levels of circulating plasma during pregnancy. When doing PA, the topic of the qualitative composition of plasma-substituting solutions typically comes up. This depends on the patient's health, the quantity of plasma taken, the frequency of PA, and the electrolyte and total protein levels in the blood. The volume of crystalloids is thought to be able to

replenish 30–40% of the circulating plasma volume (1000–1200 ml). In patients with normal serum protein level, plasma substitution with colloidal and crystalloid solutions is adequate when 50–60% (1400–2000 ml) is removed. Protein preparations must be administered in order to substitute significant volumes of withdrawn plasma (more than 60% of the total plasma volume, or more than 2000 ml) [11, 42, 43, 49].

According to the literature review, the unresolved issues with performing therapeutic PA in patients with ICP are the quantity of plasma extracted, the replenishment of the withdrawn plasma, the interval between PA sessions, and the total number of sessions. Patients with ICP continue to have issues with the quantity and caliber of plasma-substituting solutions. In addition to addressing the aforementioned issues, the current study aims to identify risk factors for the onset of intrahepatic cholestasis.

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